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Water Health Open knowLedge (WHOW)

Milestone #11: Compliance with the Metadata Quality Assurance (MQA) tool for datasets

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Abstract	Simply publishing open data is insufficient. In fact, it must answer pertinent public questions and maintain high quality over time. In response to a shift in focus advocated by the Open Knowledge Foundation, this deliverable proposes a comprehensive data quality assessment framework. The framework implements the Metadata Quality Assessment Methodology European data portal. Hence, we use the framework for assessing the compliance with DCAT-AP of the metadata associated with all the RDF datasets generated by the two data providers involved in the project (i.e. ISPRA and ARIA) that compose the WHOW Knowledge Graph. A detailed report is presented for each RDF dataset by providing the metadata used and recording the corresponding quality score.
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Table of contents

Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction	11
1.1 Project Overview.....	11
1.2 Objectives.....	11
1.3 Relationships with other activities.....	12
1.4 Structure of the document.....	13
2. The Metadata Quality Assurance (MQA)	14
2.1 Dimensions of metadata quality.....	14
2.2 Assessment of metadata quality.....	15
2.3 Enhancement of metadata quality.....	15
2.4 Metadata Quality Assessment according to the European Data Portal.....	16
3. Metadata generation and management in WHOW	19
3.1 Metadating.....	20
3.2 Validation.....	21
4. WHOW Datasets with metadata	23
4.1 Linked Open Datasets – ISPRA.....	23
4.1.1 National Tide Gauge Network - RMN.....	24
4.1.2 National Data Buoy Network - RON.....	26
4.1.3 Land Consumption.....	28
4.1.4 The Repertory of Mitigation Measures for National Soil Protection - ReNDiS.....	29
4.1.5 Bathing waters - BATHW.....	31
4.1.6 Marine indicators - MARIND.....	32
4.1.7 <i>Ostreopsis ovata</i>	34
4.1.8 Pesticides - PEST.....	35
4.1.9 Places - PLACE.....	38
4.1.10 Metadata Quality Assessment.....	39
4.2 Linked Open Datasets – ARIA.....	41
4.2.1 Hydrography Rivers.....	42
4.2.2 Hydrography Lakes.....	44
4.2.3 Water quality parameters.....	45
4.2.4 Underground waters.....	46
4.2.5 Height of lakes.....	48
4.2.6 ATS.....	48
4.2.7 Hospital stays.....	49
4.2.8 Drugs.....	51
4.2.9 Infectious diseases.....	52
4.2.10 Weather.....	53

4.2.11 Metadata Quality Assessment.....	54
5 Conclusions.....	56
References.....	57

List of Tables

- [Table 1. Groups of rating of the MQA.](#)
- [Table 2. DCAT properties used by ISPRA.](#)
- [Table 3. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for RMN.](#)
- [Table 4. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for RON.](#)
- [Table 5. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for SOILC.](#)
- [Table 6. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for ReNDiS.](#)
- [Table 7. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for BATHW.](#)
- [Table 8. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for MARIND.](#)
- [Table 9. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Ostreopsis.](#)
- [Table 10. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for PEST.](#)
- [Table 11. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Places.](#)
- [Table 12. Results obtained for the metadata of ISPRA datasets and RDF distributions.](#)
- [Table 13. DCAT properties used by ISPRA.](#)
- [Table 14. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hydrography Rivers.](#)
- [Table 15. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hydrography Lakes.](#)
- [Table 16. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Water quality parameters.](#)
- [Table 17. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Underground waters.](#)
- [Table 18. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Height of lakes.](#)
- [Table 19. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for ATS.](#)
- [Table 20. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hospital stays.](#)
- [Table 21. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hospital Drugs.](#)
- [Table 22. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hospital Infectious diseases.](#)
- [Table 23. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Weather.](#)
- [Table 24. Results obtained for the metadata of ISPRA datasets and RDF distributions.](#)

List of Figures

List Of Images

1. [Figure 1. Relationships with other deliverables and activities](#)
2. [Figure 2. RDF data generation pipeline.](#)

Executive Summary

The benefits of making open data available is not immediately apparent to data providers and consumers because they are often intangible.

For instance:

- they may help in creating insights that improve specific research and decision-making activities;
- they may be the means through which new applications, services and websites are developed;
- they may support in improving products and existing processes in order to augment productivity and efficiency;
- they may assist in understanding how to act in order to provide more sustainable actions as a society for the defence of our planet and wellbeing.

However, simply publishing open data is not enough for such advantages to become evident. It is widely acknowledged that for open data to be truly effective, it must: i) be able to answer relevant questions of public interest with respect to the reference application domain; ii) be of high quality over time, supported by sustainable processes.

In a blog post of 2017¹, the Open Knowledge Foundation clearly stated that *“The open data community needs to shift focus from mass data publication towards an understanding of good data quality.”*

In the light of these observations, we believe that an important aspect in the process of publishing open data is to give data providers any tool that can guide them in releasing open data of high quality, helping them to improve what they can obtain even at an early stage of the open data process, and to facilitate the show up of the above mentioned intangible advantages.

To do so, it is also important to understand what 'open data of high quality' means. This deliverable proposes a *data quality assessment framework* for evaluating the quality of open data according to different aspects. In particular, the framework consists of:

- a set of indicators, and associated metrics when applicable, spanning from business, strictly related to the application domain, to more technical indicators that are defined according to quality dimensions available at the state of the art;
- an evaluation mechanism that, based on priorities that can be assigned to indicators, allows data providers to understand the *level of achieved quality* for their data.

It is worth noticing that there are a certain number of evaluation frameworks that have been adopted over years in the open data context. Examples include the Open Data Maturity of the data.europa.eu portal [1], the open data certificates² from Open Data Institute (ODI), the Open Data Barometer³, the FAIR Data Maturity Model [2]. However, according to our research, these frameworks do not focus on specific relevant questions for target domains, and some of them do not take into account quality dimensions for all data aspects, from metadata of datasets to data content and data semantics. This is also due to their general

¹ <https://blog.okfn.org/2017/05/31/open-data-quality-the-next-shift-in-open-data/>.

² <https://certificates.theodi.org/en/>

³ <https://opendatabarometer.org/3rdedition/report/>

nature. In contrast, the framework proposed in this deliverable relies on indicators defined in most of these experiences while targeting the objectives of specific open data processes. This leads to the definition of a framework that is able to unify in one tool the minimum set of indicators that are significant for the open data process of a data provider, capable of guiding it in publishing data that may show a real impact on the reuse.

Among the business indicators in the framework proposed in this paper, we include some of those that have been defined in the context of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainability, identified as relevant to the WHOW project as well as thematic indicators important for answering the most crucial questions underlying the WHOW use cases.

The technical indicators instead are mainly based on the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) that, we claim, guide the openness of all the data in every application domain, not only in open science. This approach is also promoted by recent initiatives of open data communities such as the “datiBeneComune” Italian initiative, where a published online report clearly asks government institutions to open data having in mind these principles⁴. In particular, the deliverable includes technical indicators selected from the: i) FAIR Data Maturity Model; ii) ISO/IEC 25012 data quality model standard; iii) Metadata Quality Assessment model of data.europa.eu; scientific literature on the quality of the semantic of the data.

Thus, the deliverable discusses the definition of the framework, the methodologies we applied for the selection of all its indicators and extends the preliminary analysis on the data quality framework introduced in the “Use Cases Definition” deliverable.

⁴ <https://vorrei.datibenecomune.it/dati-che-vorrei/come-li-vorrei/>

1. Introduction

This is deliverable “5.1 - SDGs and KPIs are identified”. It is the result of the activities conducted in the context of task 5.2 of Activity 5 related to “Use Case Development”. It extends deliverable 2.1 “Use Cases Definition”.

1.1 Project Overview

The WHOW project aims to foster the creation of the first open and distributed European knowledge graph on water consumption and quality, health parameters and dissemination of diseases to be reused for advanced analysis and development of innovative services.

The project leverages the Linked Open Data paradigm. Water related datasets from Italy and other European countries and Copernicus (the European Union's Earth observation programme) will be used to support the construction of WHOW's knowledge graph, intended as a federation of knowledge graphs deployed at each data provider willing to join the WHOW community. The knowledge graph will be documented on data.europa.eu, the official portal for European data, thanks to the adoption of shared metadata models such as DCAT-AP and its extensions that are relevant for the type of data treated in WHOW (e.g., GeoDCAT-AP). Selected health related datasets mainly from Italy will be linked to specific water datasets.

WHOW targets identified use cases in the creation of the knowledge graph. In order to evaluate such use cases relevant set of indicators for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are identified along with Key Performance Indicators for metadata and data quality. A co-creation programme, where interested stakeholders and users are engaged from the initial phases of the project, is set-up so as to consider real needs of data re-users.

The initiative supports the Public Open Data Digital Service Infrastructure by helping to boost the development of information products and services based on the re-use and combination of environmental data and health data on disease dissemination.

1.2 Objectives

This deliverable discusses a set of selected indicators as well as an evaluation methodology for them that together form the so-called **WHOW data quality framework**.

Note that, there is no willingness here to ‘reinvent the wheel’: the WHOW data quality framework can be thought of as an aggregator of the most important indicators and metrics for open data quality that recently emerged and are dispersed in a variety of different evaluation models and tools.

The term data quality, we use to qualify the framework, encompasses not only the technical characteristics of the data, but also its ability to answer important questions that are relevant for possible re-users of the application domain(s). Therefore, the indicators composing the framework are both business indicators, that is, indicators related to the specific water and health application domains investigated in the WHOW projects, and technical indicators; that is, indicators related to different technical aspects of open datasets

such as descriptive metadata, semantics of dataset content, accessibility, interoperability. Furthermore, the framework includes indicators for monitoring the Sustainable Development Goals that have been analysed and defined as relevant to support the implementation of the WHOW use cases, already described in Deliverable 2.1⁵ [3].

From a technical perspective, the indicators included in the WHOW data quality framework are all guided by the FAIR principles, already mentioned in our previous deliverables on the WHOW architecture and use cases. We claim that any open data publication process, also carried out in a context which is different from the open science context, can be improved if those principles are at the forefront. However, these are general and agnostic of technological implementations; they are guidelines that ensure not only that data/metadata are traceable and persistent over time, but also that they are published with high quality international data representation standards in mind. Among these standards, in the WHOW data quality framework we refer to the Metadata Quality Assessment of data.europa.eu, crucial for the metadata quality evaluation, and for enabling future harvesting activities that document the produced WHOW knowledge graph in the European data portal, and the ISO/IEC 25012 and its implementing standard ISO/IEC 25024 on the data quality model. In particular, from these latter standards, we select according to a policy we describe in this deliverable, a set of relevant data quality characteristics and their associated indicators and metrics that we want to assess when releasing open datasets. Finally, since an important role in the WHOW project is played by the harmonised semantic conceptualisation of the datasets forming the knowledge graph, indicators of the semantic soundness are listed, as presented in the reference scientific literature.

To conclude, we state that the proposed WHOW data quality framework may allow data providers and consumers to assess the readiness, implementation and impact of the WHOW knowledge graph.

1.3 Relationships with other activities

The present deliverable D5.1 is another important milestone (#9) of the WHOW project. It covers all the activities of task 5.2 of Activity 5 that have dependencies linked with other tasks of other activities of the project.

The following Figure 1 shows such relationships. In particular, the content of this deliverable; that is, the results of the activities of task 5.2, is both related to the definition of the use cases and the preliminary data quality requirements there identified, and the design of the technical architecture. In addition, relationships with the on-going work of the semantic data model of the knowledge graph of WHOW are identified when semantic indicators are described and included in the framework introduced in this document.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685761>

Figure 1. Relationships with other deliverables and activities

1.4 Structure of the document

The rest of this document is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the WHOW data quality framework with the set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have been identified. Section 3 introduces the business KPIs distinguishing between the selected Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of Agenda ONU 2020 from the thematic KPIs we defined for supporting the three use cases of the project. Section 4 describes the technical KPIs for the assessment of the quality of the produced WHOW knowledge graph. Technical KPIs are discussed from different perspectives according to the FAIR principles. Finally, Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

2. The Metadata Quality Assurance (MQA)

Metadata quality plays a pivotal role in data management and information retrieval systems. High-quality metadata enhances data discovery, ensures data accuracy, and facilitates data integration. The Directive EU 2019/1024 aims to promote the use of open data, related metadata and data reuse providing a homogeneous and shared framework that includes the availability of open APIs and the use of open data formats recognized at the international level.

Metadata literally means “data about data” and is essential for effective data management. Metadata quality, in this context, refers to the accuracy, completeness, consistency, and relevancy of metadata associated with a dataset. Poor metadata quality can lead to data misinterpretation, reduced data usability, and inefficiencies in data-related processes. By adopting systematic assessment methods and best practices, organisations can enhance metadata quality, thereby improving data-driven decision-making processes and promoting data interoperability.

2.1 Dimensions of metadata quality

Metadata quality encompasses various dimensions [4], [5], including:

1. **Accuracy:** Metadata should accurately reflect the underlying data as inaccurate metadata can lead to misinterpretation and unreliable data analysis.
2. **Completeness:** Metadata should provide a comprehensive description of the dataset, including all relevant attributes, properties, and relationships.
3. **Consistency:** Metadata should follow consistent naming conventions, data formats, and terminology. Inconsistencies can confuse users and hinder data integration.
4. **Relevancy:** Metadata should contain information that is relevant to the dataset and its intended use. Irrelevant metadata adds noise and reduces the usability of data.
5. **Timeliness:** Metadata should be up-to-date and reflect changes in the dataset. Outdated metadata can lead to confusion and incorrect data usage.
6. **Interoperability:** Metadata should be structured in a way that allows for easy integration with other datasets and systems. Interoperable metadata enhances data sharing and reuse.
7. **Accessibility:** Metadata should be easily accessible to users, both humans and machines. Proper access controls should be in place to protect sensitive metadata.

The WHOW data quality framework adopts the indicators defined in the Metadata Quality Assessment of data.europa.eu, which are key for future data integration with the data.europa.eu portal as also stated in the WHOW Deliverable 5.1 (Milestone #9)⁶ [6].

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685733>

2.2 Assessment of metadata quality

Assessing metadata quality typically requires a systematic approach. According to the literature, several methods and tools can be employed:

1. **Manual Inspection:** Human experts review metadata records to identify issues related to accuracy, completeness, and consistency. This method is time-consuming but provides detailed insights.
2. **Metadata Standards Compliance:** Evaluate metadata against established standards like Dublin Core⁷, MODS⁸, or schema.org⁹ to ensure compliance and consistency [7]. This can happen through machine learning techniques. Indeed, it is possible to employ machine learning algorithms to automatically enrich and assess metadata quality, identifying patterns and anomalies in large datasets [8]–[12]. In this context, the most up-to-date and standard tool is the MQA tool provided by data.europa.eu¹⁰, checking compliance with DCAT-AP and its derivatives, data accessibility, machine readability and licences.
3. **Metadata Profiling:** Use automated tools to create metadata profiles, summarising key statistics and anomalies. This approach can quickly identify issues such as missing values or inconsistent formats [13].
4. **User Feedback:** Gather feedback from data users to identify any difficulties or concerns related to metadata quality. This approach provides real-world insights into usability [14].
5. **Data Quality Metrics:** Implement data quality metrics that assess metadata quality alongside data quality. Metrics can quantify aspects like completeness, accuracy, and timeliness.

2.3 Enhancement of metadata quality

The inadequacy in metadata quality poses a significant struggle for users when it comes to retrieving and exploring information that caters to their needs. Enhancing this aspect is therefore imperative to improve the accessibility of its contents. As shown by [15], the lack in metadata quality is directly correlated to the failure in retrieving relevant documents. This issue has been recently evaluated by several studies about Open Data portals (see for instance [16]), where it is indicated that many of the evaluated data sets either lacked metadata or showcased a simplistic version of them. When delving into specific factors impacting Open Government Data (OGD) and metadata quality, [17] for example discovered that centralised data disclosure, characterised by standardised data structures, results in higher quality data and metadata as compared to decentralised disclosure, where there's no common data structure. On a similar note, [18] noted that national portals operating on CKAN platform secured better quality scores compared to others. Conversely, [19] found that US cities' portals based on the Socrata platform performed better, as evidenced by their overall portal score.

⁷ <https://www.dublincore.org/>.

⁸ <http://www.loc.gov/standards/mods/>.

⁹ <https://schema.org/>.

¹⁰ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology>.

By improving the metadata quality, not only is the accuracy of retrieval enhanced, but it also paves the way for a more user-centric and efficient information exploration experience. To achieve this goal, organisations should consider the following best practices:

1. **Standardise Metadata:** Adhere to established metadata standards and vocabularies to ensure consistency and interoperability.
2. **Metadata Documentation:** Create detailed documentation that explains metadata elements, their definitions, and usage guidelines.
3. **Automate Metadata Capture:** Use automation tools to capture metadata during data creation or ingestion processes to reduce errors and omissions.
4. **Regular Updates:** Implement a process for regularly updating metadata to reflect changes in the dataset.
5. **User Training:** Train data contributors and users on metadata best practices to promote accurate and consistent metadata creation and usage.
6. **Metadata Governance:** Establish metadata governance policies and assign responsibilities for metadata quality management.
7. **Metadata Validation:** Enforce metadata validation rules to ensure data quality at the point of entry.

2.4 Metadata Quality Assessment according to the European Data Portal

The official portal of European data, data.europa.eu, highlights three main points that make up a guideline for any project concerned with metadata production:

1. The use of a common reference metadata schema;
2. The consistent reuse of terms and metadata according to specific definitions of a schema;
3. The attention towards metadata quality, according to a methodology of analysis and evaluation based on specific metrics.

For what concerns this last point, at the European level, the EU has released the Metadata Quality Assessment tool¹¹. Such a tool supports the development of a dashboard to provide an overview of the contents harvested from the different catalogues contributing to the European Data Portal, and aims at assisting data providers and data portals in assessing their metadata against a range of 23 metrics classified in five dimensions, mainly focused on the adoption of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles¹². Those principles underscore the importance of machine-actionability, meaning the ability of computational systems to independently discover, access, interact with, and recycle data with minimal or no human intervention. This emphasis is driven by the growing dependence on computational assistance due

¹¹ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/?locale=en>.

¹² <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

to the escalating volume, intricacy, and rapid generation of data. The criteria¹³ focused by the EU Metadata Quality Assessment tool are:

- **Final rating evolution**, meant to assign a rating category from ‘Bad’ to ‘Excellent’ basing on the range of point obtained from the total of all the categories;
- **Findability**, which is an indicator to measure how much people and machines can easily find a target dataset based on aspects such as keywords usage, use of spatial and temporal information and the presence of the possibility to explore the datasets thematically. A maximum of 100 points can be scored is assigned to this indicator;
- **Accessibility**, which is an indicator to determine whether access to the data referenced by the distributions is guaranteed. Again, a maximum of 100 points can be scored is assigned to this indicator;
- **Interoperability**, which is an indicator used to determine whether a distribution is considered interoperable. The metrics considered for this include checking if the format of the distribution is set, checking the media type of the distribution, verifying if the format and media type belong to a controlled vocabulary, ensuring the format of the distribution is non-proprietary and machine-readable, and finally, checking for DCAT-AP compliance. A total of 110 points can be scored in this dimension.
- **Reusability**, which is an indicator to check the reusability of the data. The metrics for this include checking if licence information is set, ensuring the use of controlled vocabularies for licences, verifying if access restrictions are indicated and if a controlled vocabulary for access rights is used, checking if a contact point is provided, and lastly, verifying if a publisher is set. A maximum of 75 points can be scored for this indicator.
- **Contextuality**, which provides additional context to the user about the dataset. Metrics for this category include checking if the ‘Rights’ field is filled out, verifying the file size in bytes, checking the date the dataset or distribution was issued, and the modification date of the dataset or distribution. A total of 20 points can be scored in this dimension.

This process is also based on the assumption that filling the DCAT-AP mandatory fields alone is not enough to provide high-quality metadata, therefore the fields that are checked for also include those that are not specified as mandatory according to the DCAT-AP (e.g. *DownloadURL*).

The EU Metadata Quality Assessment tool serves as a reference framework in the WHOW project to evaluate metadata quality of the produced datasets. Depending on the points achieved, datasets can be rated as Excellent, Good, Sufficient, or Bad.

¹³ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology?locale=en>.

3. Metadata generation and management in WHOW

Based on the architectural design proposed in Deliverable 3.2¹⁴ [20], a framework known as WHOW toolkit has been developed. The toolkit is a Python software available as open source on a GitHub repository¹⁵ of the WHOW project. It provides a set of independent components for defining sustainable pipelines for open knowledge graph production that guarantees authoritativeness, timeliness, semantic accuracy and consistency data quality characteristics, as well as compliance of metadata with the European DCAT-AP profile and related national and thematic extensions.

Different scenarios are considered according to the data provider. For what concerns Aria, the data owner shares with the open data team the dataset metadata, through a dedicated metadata sheet, with information on title, description, frequency of the update and last update, data category, licence type. For subsequent changes and integrations, there is an automated process. Then, the metadata files and datasets are published and updated according to automatic, semi-automatic, and manual modes. In the ISPRA pipeline, automatic tools generally perform db queries, field selection within a Shapefile, download of measurement collections and metadata information by monitoring stations and generate CSV files, which contain all relevant information to be published.

The pipeline ends with the publication of open datasets in a rich open data catalogue, where all datasets are accompanied by metadata compliant with DCAT-AP(_IT) version 1.1. A typical pipeline that can be implemented with the WHOW toolkit is represented in Figure 1. In such a pipeline *Metadating* and *Validation* are outlined in red as they represent the activities of generating metadata compliant with the European DCAT-AP profile and validating and performing the metadata quality assessment for such metadata schema, respectively. The other activities are responsible for: (i) ingesting non-RDF datasets into the framework; (ii) preprocessing the dataset (e.g. charset conversion, standardisation of dates, etc.); (iii) generation of RDF triples by means of RML mapping; (iv) publication of the RDF triples on a triplestore and the metadata on a data catalogue.

Figure 2. RDF data generation pipeline.

Each activity is implemented by a dedicated component of the WHOW toolkit. That is, for metadating and validation these components are the Metadata Manager¹⁶ and Validation Manager¹⁷, respectively.

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685697>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/whow-project/architecture/tree/main/whow-toolkit>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/whow-project/architecture/tree/main/whow-toolkit/WHOWToolkit/metadata>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/whow-project/architecture/tree/main/whow-toolkit/WHOWToolkit/validator>

3.1 Metadating

The Metadata Manager accepts as input a reference (i.e. a URI) to an RDF graph generated by the triplification activity, a configuration file with .ini extension, and two URIs for identifying in the metadata catalogue the dataset and the distribution. The configuration file consists of a text-based content with a structure and syntax comprising key–value pairs for properties, and sections that organise the properties. The keys are DCAT-AP properties and values are their corresponding valorisation. Those key–value pairs can be organised into two sections, i.e. one for DCAT-AP metadata for describing a dataset and another for DCAT-AP metadata for describing a dataset distribution. The Metadata Manager uses the dataset URI provided as input to retrieve existing metadata available in the catalogue. The output produced by the Metadata Manager is an RDF representation of the configuration file, which is eventually enriched with already existing metadata from the catalogue and packaged along with the input RDF dataset for further processing (e.g. Validation). The following is an example of a configuration file, in which sections are coloured in red, whilst key-value pairs are separated by the = symbol.

[dataset]

```
# https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/bathw/dataset
dct:identifier='ispra_rm:bathw_Series'
dct:title='Dataset acque di balneazione'@it
dct:title='Bathing waters Dataset'@en
dct:description='Dataset indicatori acque di balneazione'@it
dct:description='Bathing Water Indicator Dataset'@en
dcat:theme=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>
dct:modified='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
dct:rightsHolder=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
dct:accrualPeriodicity=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
dct:subject=<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/600>
dcat:contactPoint=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD>
dct:publisher=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
dct:creator=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
dct:issued='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
dct:language=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>
dct:language=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG>
dcat:keyword='open data'@it
dcat:keyword='open data'@en
dcat:keyword='balneazione'@it
dcat:keyword='bathing'@en
dcat:keyword='mare'@it
dcat:keyword='sea'@en
dcat:keyword='turismo'@it
dcat:keyword='tourism'@en
dcat:keyword='salute'@it
dcat:keyword='health'@en
dct:temporal=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/20220101_today>
```

```
dct:spatial=<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classification/countries/italy/ITA>
dct:spatial=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>
dct:spatial=<https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
dct:accessRights=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
prov:wasDerivedFrom=<https://doi.org/10.2909/5d9a4d94-511a-486d-afbb-4f01e5c73e23>
```

[distribution]

```
# https://w3id.org/italia/env/Ld/bathw/distribution/nt
dcat:accessURL=<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
dct:format=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
dct:license=<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
dct:description='Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset indicatori acque di balneazione'@it
dct:description='RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the bathing water indicators dataset'@en
dct:title='Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset acque di balneazione'@it
dct:title='RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the bathing water dataset'@en
dcat:downloadURL=<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/bathw/kg>
dct:modified='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
dcat:mediaType=<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
dct:rights=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
dct:issued='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
```

3.2 Validation

The Validation Manager accepts a package that contains an RDF distribution of a dataset and its DCAT-AP metadata as RDF. Then it first performs a validation based on the SHACL shapes of the SEMIC's specification¹⁸. This validation uses all shapes (base, vocabularies, recommended properties, and ranges) for testing the compliance of metadata produced by the toolkit against the DCAT-AP version 2.0.1 specification. Then, if the SHACL based validation is passed then a Metadata Quality Assessment (MQA) is performed. For this the Validation Manager implements the MQA methodology proposed by the official portal for European data¹⁹. Hence, the Validation Manager computes the scores for each indicator associated with the different dimensions (i.e. Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability, and Contextuality). Following the same rationale as the portal for European data, the ultimate rating is determined through four distinct rating groups, and the correlation between points and rating categories is detailed in the accompanying table. In the MQA, the portrayal of the rating exclusively relies on these categories. The four groups of rating are reported in Table 1.

¹⁸ <https://github.com/SEMICeu/DCAT-AP/releases/tag/v2.0.1>

¹⁹ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology?locale=en>

Table 1. Groups of rating of the MQA.

RATING	RANGE OF POINTS
Excellent	351 - 405
Good	221 – 350
Sufficient	121 – 220
Bad	0 - 120

The reimplementation of the MQA of the portal for European data within the toolkit allows the Validator Manager to raise an error message in case the rating of the DCAT-AP associated with an RDF distribution of a dataset is below a given acceptance threshold. Accordingly, the publication activity is only carried out in case the Validator Manager does not raise any error. Such a publication activity allows the toolkit to upload the RDF distribution in (i) a provided triplestore for accessing the data via SPARQL and (ii) a provided storage for enabling download. Additionally, the DCAT-AP compliant metadata are uploaded in the data catalogue. In the specific case of WHOW there are two data providers (i.e. ISPRA and ARIA) whose data catalogue are then harvested by the Italian National Data Catalogue²⁰, which in turn is harvested by the European Data Catalogue²¹. The latter finally computes the MQA for each data catalogue at national level by means of the MQA tool.

The source code of the SHACL validation and MQA is available on GitHub²².

²⁰ <https://dati.gov.it/>

²¹ <https://data.europa.eu/>

²²

https://github.com/whow-project/architecture/blob/main/whow-toolkit/WHOWToolkit/validator/shacl_validator_core.py

4. WHOW Datasets with metadata

We produced linked open datasets along with their corresponding metadata for both data providers involved in the project, that is ISPRA and ARIA. In the following subsections we provide the details of published datasets for them separately.

4.1 Linked Open Datasets – ISPRA

The Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research²³ (ISPRA) produced and published 9 RDF distributions of as many datasets. The details for each distribution are reported in the following subsections. All the resources in the RDF distribution use persistent URIs by means of the w3id.org²⁴ service run by the Permanent Identifier Community Group²⁵. The base namespace adopted by ISPRA is:

`https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/`

and URIs are generated following the schema

`https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/{dataset_id}/{entity_type}/{entity_id}`

where:

- `dataset_id` is the placeholder for the dataset identifier, e.g. ron, rmn, bathw, etc.;
- `entity_type` is the placeholder the the entity type, e.g. observationseries;
- `entity_id` is the placeholder for the entity identifier, e.g. 00105_an15_airpressure_202201.

Accordingly, https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/rmn/observationseries/00105_an15_airpressure_202201 is an example of URI generated to uniquely and persistently identify the series of observation of atmospheric pressure data recorded in Ancona during January 2022.

Table 2 reports the properties of the Italian Profile of DCAT-AP²⁶ (DCAPT-AP_IT) used for metadating all the data produced by ISPRA at dataset and distribution level, respectively.

Table 2. DCAT properties used by ISPRA.

Subject	DCAT property
Dataset	Mandatory properties <ul style="list-style-type: none">• dct:identifier• dct:title• dct:description

²³ The Italian name is: Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale

²⁴ <https://w3id.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.w3.org/community/perma-id/>

²⁶ <https://www.dati.gov.it/content/dcat-ap-it-v10-profilo-italiano-dcat-ap-0>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:theme ● dct:modified ● dct:rightsHolder ● dct:accrualPeriodicity <p>Recommended properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dct:subject ● dcat:contactPoint ● dct:publisher <p>Optional properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dct:creator ● dct:issued ● dct:language ● dcat:keyword ● dct:temporal ● dct:spatial ● dct:accessRights
Distribution	<p>Mandatory properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:accessURL ● dct:format ● dct:license <p>Recommended properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dct:description ● dct:title <p>Optional properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:downloadURL ● dct:modified ● dcat:mediaType ● dct:rights ● dct:issued

4.1.1 National Tide Gauge Network - RMN

The National Tide Gauge Network (RMN) is made up of 36 measure stations, evenly distributed across the national territory and located mainly inside the port infrastructures. All stations are equipped with a local system for data management and storage while at ISPRA's headquarters in Rome there is a real-time data transmission device (UMTS). In addition, in 9 strategic stations for measurement of particular phenomena (anomalous waves) there is a second data transmission system via IRIDIUM satellite, which ensures connection also in the case of a UMTS blackout. Since the new National Tide Gauge Network became fully operational, ISPRA can make available for users updated information related to historical series, real-time observations, data forecast for astronomical tide, data analysis for planning and scientific purposes. RMN includes observational data on tide gauges in Italy with details about:

- Sea Level (metres);
- Water Temperature (degrees C);
- Air Temperature (degrees C);
- Humidity (%);
- Atmospheric pressure (hPa);
- Wind direction (degrees N);
- Wind speed (m/s).

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/rmn/dataset>.

Table 3. reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for RMN.

Table 3. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for RMN.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:rmn_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset RMN'@it, 'RMN Dataset'@en,
	dct:description	'Dataset RMN (Rete Mareografica Nazionale)'@it, 'RMN Dataset (Italian national tide gauge network)'@en
	dcat:theme	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI >
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/CONT >
	dct:subject	< http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2114 >, < http://eurovoc.europa.eu/1278 >, < http://eurovoc.europa.eu/c_a935cf3f >, < http://eurovoc.europa.eu/89 >
	dcat:contactPoint	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-COS-CLM >
	dct:publisher	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:creator	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA >, < http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG >
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'maree'@it, 'tide'@en, 'mare'@it, 'sea'@en, 'nazionale'@it, 'nazional'@en, 'rete'@it, 'network'@en, 'rmn'@it, 'mareografica'@it
	dct:temporal	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/19980101_today >
	dct:spatial	< https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA >, < http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA >, < https://www.geonames.org/3175395 >
dct:accessRights	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC >	

Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset RMN'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the RMN dataset'@en
	dct:title	"'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset RMN'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the RMN dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/rmn/kg>
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.2 National Data Buoy Network - RON

The National Data Buoy Network (RON) is the dataset about wave motion recorded by a network of 15 measure stations located at fixed points along the national coasts to collect data which, duly processed, characterise sea state. The descriptive parameters derive from the continuous observation of variations in sea surface through directional buoys and are processed at regular time intervals after the definition in no. 702 guideline “Guide to wave analysis and forecasting” from the World Meteorological Organization²⁷ (WMO).

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/ron/dataset>

Table 4 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for RON.

Table 4. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for RON.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:ron_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset RON'@it, dct:title,'RON Dataset'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset RON (Rete Ondametrica Nazionale)'@it, 'RON Dataset (Italian national data buoy network)'@en
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date

²⁷ <https://wmo.int/>

	dct:rightsHolder	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/CONT>
	dct:subject	<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2114>
	dcat:contactPoint	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-COS-CLM>
	dct:publisher	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:creator	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>, <dct:language,<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG>
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'onde marine'@it, 'Ocean waves'@en, 'boa'@it, 'buoy'@en, 'nazionale'@it, 'nazional'@en, 'mare'@it, 'sea'@en, 'onda'@it, 'wave'@en, 'onde'@it, 'waves'@en, 'rete'@it, 'newtork'@en, 'ron'@it, 'ondametrico'@it, 'ondametria'@it, 'ondametrica'@it
	dct:temporal	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/19890101_today>
	dct:spatial	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>, <dct:spatial,<https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset RON'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the RON dataset'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset RON'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the RON dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/ron/kg>
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.3 Land Consumption

The Land Consumption (SOILC) dataset provides linked open data on land consumption in Italy ensures the availability of quantitative estimates over the whole territory and could be integrated with other high resolution cartographic sources to derive several indicators.

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/soilc/dataset>.

Table 5 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for SOILC.

Table 5. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for SOILC.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:soilc_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset indicatori consumo del suolo'@it, 'Dataset of Land consumption indicators'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset indicatori consumo del suolo'@it, 'Dataset of Land consumption indicators'@en
	dcat:theme	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI >, < https://open-iacs-project.eu/datasets/dcat/environmental >
	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL >
	dct:subject	< http://eurovoc.europa.eu/4630 >
	dcat:contactPoint	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD >
	dct:publisher	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:creator	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA >,< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG >
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'Consumo del suolo'@it, 'Land consumption'@en, 'Suolo'@it, 'Land'@en, 'Suolo consumato'@it, 'Land consumed'@en, 'Uso del suolo'@it, 'Land Use'@en
	dct:temporal	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/20060101_today >
dct:spatial	< https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA >, < http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA >, < https://www.geonames.org/3175395 >	
dct:accessRights	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC >	

Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset Indicatori di Consumo del suolo'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the Land Consumption Indicators dataset'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset Indicatori di Consumo del suolo'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the Land Consumption Indicators dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/soilc/kg>
	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.4 The Repertory of Mitigation Measures for National Soil Protection - ReNDiS

ReNDiS aims at realising a homogeneous database of the measures and resources committed to soil protection and risk mitigation.

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/dissesto/dataset>.

Table 6 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for ReNDiS.

Table 6. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for ReNDiS.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:ITA_Rendis_interventiDifesaSuolo'
	dct:title	'Dataset Interventi difesa del suolo'@it, 'Dataset of Mitigation measures for national soil protection'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset Interventi difesa del suolo'@it, 'Dataset of Mitigation measures for national soil protection'@en
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>, <https://open-iacs-project.eu/datasets/dcat/environmental>, dcat:theme,<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/GOVE>
	dct:modified	'2023-10-29'^^xsd:date

	dct:rightsHolder	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/DAILY>
	dct:subject	<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/371>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/1440>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/3158>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/413>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/c_3f9a7b14>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2825>
	dcat:contactPoint	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD>
	dct:publisher	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:creator	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'hydrogeological instability'@en, 'dissesto idrogeologico'@it
	dct:temporal	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/19810101_today>
	dct:spatial	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>, <https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset Interventi difesa del suolo'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the dataset Mitigation measures for national soil protection'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset Interventi difesa del suolo'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the Mitigation measures for national soil protection dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/ih/kg/dissesto.nt.gz>
	dct:modified	'2023-10-29'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.5 Bathing waters - BATHW

Directive 2006/7/EC concerning the management of bathing water quality, transposed in Italy by Legislative Decree No 116 of 30 May 2008 and implemented by the Ministry of Health Decree of 30 March 2010, provides that each water is assigned a quality class (excellent, good, sufficient and poor). BATHW (Bathing waters) provides a linked open dataset with indicator about the number of waters falling into each class, and is drawn up on the basis of “seasonal information” published in the European Environment Agency’s Country Report²⁸ derived from the annual Community Report that the Ministry of Health prepares based on the results of monitoring carried out by ARPAs and Regional Health Authorities. The indicator provides an indicative description of the qualitative state of bathing water at the microbiological level.

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/bathw/dataset>.

Table 7 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for BATHW.

Table 7. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for BATHW.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:bathw_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset acque di balneazione'@it, 'Bathing waters Dataset'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset indicatori acque di balneazione'@it, 'Bathing Water Indicator Dataset'@en
	dcat:theme	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI >
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL >
	dct:subject	< http://eurovoc.europa.eu/600 >
	dcat:contactPoint	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD >
	dct:publisher	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:creator	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:issued	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA >, < http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG >
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'balneazione'@it, 'bathing'@en, 'mare'@it, 'sea'@en, 'turismo'@it, 'tourism'@en, 'salute'@it, 'health'@en
dct:temporal	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/19900101_today >	

	dct:spatial	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>, <https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	prov:wasDerivedFrom	<https://doi.org/10.2909/5d9a4d94-511a-486d-afbb-4f01e5c73e23>
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset indicatori acque di balneazione'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the bathing water indicators dataset'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset acque di balneazione'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the bathing water dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/bathw/kg>
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.6 Marine indicators - MARIND

This dataset provides marine indicators computed from earth observations.

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/marind/dataset>.

Table 8 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for MARIND.

Table 8. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for MARIND.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:marind_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset indicatori marini'@it, 'Marine indicators Dataset'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset indicatori marini da osservazioni della terra'@it, 'Marine indicator dataset from earth observations'@en
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>

	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:subject	<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/940>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/c_a935cf3f>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2114>
	dcat:contactPoint	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD>
	dct:publisher	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:creator	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:issued	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG>
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'indicatore'@it, 'indicators'@en, 'mare'@it, 'sea'@en, 'dato spaziale'@it, 'spatial data'@en, 'osservazione terra'@it, 'earth observation'@en
	dct:temporal	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/20200101_today>
	dct:spatial	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>, <https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset indicatori marini da osservazioni della terra'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the marine indicators dataset from earth observations'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset indicatori marini'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the marine indicators dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/marind/kg>
	dct:modified	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-11-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.7 *Ostreopsis ovata*

This dataset contains observation of the spread of *ostreopsis ovata* on Italian coasts. The presence of the potentially toxic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis ovata* (Fukuyo) has been observed along the Italian coast since the '90s. From then, intense and recurrent blooms of this seaweed alga occurred in several locations of the Tyrrhenian Sea and Adriatic Sea. To date, *ostreopsis ovata* has been reported in most Italian coastal regions.

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/ostreopsis/dataset>.

Table 9 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for *Ostreopsis*.

Table 9. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Ostreopsis.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:ostreopsis_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset <i>Ostreopsis ovata</i> '@it, ' <i>Ostreopsis ovata</i> Dataset'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset osservazioni di <i>Ostreopsis ovata</i> '@it, 'Dataset of <i>Ostreopsis ovata</i> observations'@en
	dcat:theme	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI >
	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL >
	dct:subject	< http://eurovoc.europa.eu/3149 >, < http://eurovoc.europa.eu/600 >
	dcat:contactPoint	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD >
	dct:publisher	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:creator	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001 >
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA >, < http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG >
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'mare'@it, 'sea'@en, 'alga'@it, 'seaweed'@en, 'ambiente'@it, 'environment'@en, 'salute'@it, 'health'@en, 'ostreopsis'
	dct:temporal	< https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/20180101_today >
dct:spatial	< https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA >, < http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA >, < https://www.geonames.org/3175395 >	
dct:accessRights	< http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC >	
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	< https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql >

dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset osservazioni di Ostreopsis ovata'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the dataset observations of Ostreopsis ovata'@en
dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset Ostreopsis ovata'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the Ostreopsis ovata dataset'@en
dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/ostreopsis/kg>
dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.8 Pesticides - PEST

Pesticides are chemicals used to control weeds, insects and other pests in agricultural areas, and a variety of other land-use settings. Pesticides can be distinguished, from a regulatory point of view, among substances used in plant protection products and in biocidal products, which are used in various fields (disinfectants, wood preservatives, pesticides for non agricultural use, antifouling, etc.). The Regions and Autonomous Provinces carry out monitoring within the framework of the survey programmes provided for by Legislative Decree No. 152 of 3 April 2006 [D. Lgs. 152/2006], transmit the results to ISPRA, which processes and evaluates them. ISPRA provides the technical-scientific guidelines for the programming of monitoring. Moreover, the Institute feeds some of the indicators provided for by the National Action Plan for the sustainable use of plant protection products (NAP), established by the decree of 15 July 2015 [DM 172/2015]. The levels of contamination are compared with the regulatory limits for surface water and for groundwater. Environmental Quality Standards (EQS), set for surface water in the context of the WFD, are concentrations of pollutants or group of pollutants in water, sediment or biota which should not be exceeded in order to protect human health and the environment. The derivation of EQS is based on the knowledge of the levels of acute and chronic toxicity of the species representative of three trophic levels of the aquatic environment. The Directive 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater, sets standards of environmental quality, defined as the concentrations which should not be exceeded in order to protect the human health and the environment.

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/pest/dataset>.

Table 10 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for PEST.

Table 10. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for PEST.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:pest_Series'
	dct:title	'Dataset pesticidi: indicatori SQA e stazioni di monitoraggio'@it, 'Pesticide Dataset: EQS Indicators and Monitoring Stations'@en
	dct:description	<p>"I pesticidi, da un punto di vista normativo, comprendono i prodotti fitosanitari (Reg. CE 1107/2009), utilizzati per la protezione delle piante e per la conservazione dei prodotti vegetali, e i biocidi (Reg. UE 528/2012), impiegati in vari campi di attività (disinfettanti, preservanti, pesticidi per uso non agricolo, ecc.). Spesso i due tipi di prodotti utilizzano gli stessi principi attivi.</p> <p>Le Regioni e le Province Autonome realizzano il monitoraggio nell'ambito dei programmi di rilevazione previsti dal decreto legislativo 3 aprile 2006, n. 152 [D. Lgs. 152/2006], trasmettono i risultati all'ISPRA, che li elabora e valuta. L'ISPRA fornisce gli indirizzi tecnico scientifici per la programmazione del monitoraggio. L'Istituto, inoltre, alimenta alcuni degli indicatori previsti dal Piano d'Azione Nazionale per l'uso sostenibile dei prodotti fitosanitari (PAN), stabilito con il decreto 15 luglio 2015 [DM 172/2015]</p> <p>Le concentrazioni dei residui di pesticidi sono confrontate con i limiti nelle acque stabiliti a livello europeo e nazionale, definiti Standard di Qualità Ambientale (SQA). Per standard di qualità ambientale, come specificato nella Direttiva Quadro Acque (DQA -Direttiva 2000/60/CE), si intende 'la concentrazione di un particolare inquinante o gruppo di inquinanti nelle acque, nei sedimenti e nel biota che non deve essere superata, per tutelare la salute umana e l'ambiente'.</p> <p>Gli standard di qualità ambientale si basano sui livelli di tossicità di tipo acuto e cronico per le specie rappresentative dell'ambiente acquatico.</p> <p>La Direttiva 2006/118/CE sulla protezione delle acque sotterranee stabilisce norme di qualità ambientale, definiti come la concentrazione di un determinato inquinante, gruppo di inquinanti o indicatore di inquinamento nelle acque sotterranee che non dovrebbe essere superata al fine di proteggere la salute umana e l'ambiente.</p> <p>Il dataset contiene informazioni relative all'anagrafica delle stazioni di monitoraggio e ai livelli di contaminazione, ottenuti dal confronto con i limiti di legge (Standard di qualità ambientale, SQA). Per ogni punto di monitoraggio è possibile consultare le informazioni geografiche, il livello di contaminazione, i pesticidi cercati e trovati e i dati statistici sul monitoraggio.'</p> <p>@it, 'Pesticides are chemicals used to control weeds, insects and other pests in agricultural areas, and a variety of other land-use settings. Pesticides can be distinguished, from a regulatory point of view, among substances used in plant protection products and in biocidal products, which are used in various fields (disinfectants, wood preservatives, pesticides for non agricultural use, antifouling, etc.).</p> <p>The Regions and Autonomous Provinces carry out monitoring within the framework of the survey programmes provided for by Legislative Decree No. 152 of 3 April 2006 [D. Lgs. 152/2006], transmit the results to ISPRA, which processes and evaluates them. ISPRA provides the technical-scientific guidelines for the programming of monitoring. Moreover, the Institute feeds some of the indicators provided for by the National Action Plan for the sustainable use of plant protection products (NAP), established by the decree of 15 July 2015 [DM 172/2015].</p> <p>The levels of contamination are compared with the regulatory limits for surface water and for groundwater. Environmental Quality Standards (EQS), set for surface water in the context of the WFD, are concentrations of pollutants or group of pollutants in water, sediment or biota which should not be exceeded in order to</p>

		protect human health and the environment.\nThe derivation of EQS is based on the knowledge of the levels of acute and chronic toxicity of the\nspecies representative of three trophic levels of the aquatic environment.\nThe Directive 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater, sets standards of environmental quality,\nundefined as the concentrations which should not be exceeded in order to protect the human health and\nthe environment.\nThe dataset contains information on the register of monitoring stations and contamination levels obtained by comparison with legal limits (Environmental Quality Standards, EQS). For each monitoring point, it is possible to consult geographical information, contamination level, pesticides searched and found, and statistical data on monitoring.'@en"
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>
	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:subject	<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2739>
	dcat:contactPoint	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD>
	dct:publisher	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:creator	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'LoQ'@it, 'LoQ'@en, 'SQA'@it, 'EQS'@en, 'metaboliti'@it, 'metabolites'@en, 'pesticidi'@it, 'pesticides'@en
	dct:temporal	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/20180101_today>
	dct:spatial	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>, <https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset pesticidi: indicatori SQA e stazioni di monitoraggio'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the pesticide dataset: EQS indicators and monitoring stations'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset pesticidi: indicatori SQA e stazioni di monitoraggio'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the pesticide dataset: EQS indicators and monitoring stations'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/pest/kg>

	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.9 Places - PLACE

This dataset contains data related to Italian regions, provinces and municipalities (Source: data processing by the Italian National Institute of Statistics – ISTAT). The dataset is of utmost importance for integrating its diversified sources of origin. Particular attention was paid to the standardisation of geographical landmarks which, due to technical and “historical” reasons, were sometimes reduplicated in the single systems. It includes:

- Official name of places;
- Centroids for Latitude and longitude data;
- Polygons (shapes);
- Administrative hierarchy;
- ISTAT Code;
- Link to the Linked Data Cloud (ISTAT datiopen, geonames, dbpedia, etc.).

The dataset is identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/place/dataset>.

Table 11 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Places.

Table 11. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Places.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:identifier	'ispra_rm:DT_place01'
	dct:title	'Dataset dei luoghi amministrativi e ambientali'@it, 'Dataset of administrative and environmental places'@en
	dct:description	'Dataset dei luoghi amministrativi e ambientali'@it, 'Dataset of administrative and environmental places'@en
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>, <https://open-iacs-project.eu/datasets/dcat/geo_units>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/REGI>
	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:subject	<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/1520>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/4709>,

		<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/610>, <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/833>
	dcat:contactPoint	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD>
	dct:publisher	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:creator	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dct:language	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>
	dcat:keyword	'open data'@it, 'open data'@en, 'administrative units'@en, 'unit\† amministrative'@it, 'places'@en, 'luoghi'@it
	dct:temporal	<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/19910101_today>
	dct:spatial	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>, <https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dcat:accessURL	<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset dei luoghi amministrativi e ambientali'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the administrative and environmental places dataset'@en
	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset dei luoghi amministrativi e ambientali'@it, 'RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the administrative and environmental places dataset'@en
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/place/kg>
	dct:modified	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date
	dcat:mediaType	<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:issued	'2023-01-01'^^xsd:date

4.1.10 Metadata Quality Assessment

Table 12 reports the results we recorded according to the Metadata Quality Assessment Methodology²⁹ formalised by the official portal for European data computed with the metadata validation tool of the WHOW Toolkit described in [Chapter 3](#). The global rating recorded is 400 for all the datasets provided by

²⁹ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology?locale=en>

ISPRA and their corresponding RDF distributions. This result is rated as excellent according to the range of points established by the MQA formalised by the official portal for European data.

Table 12. Results obtained for the metadata of ISPRA datasets and RDF distributions.

Dimension	Indicator	RMN	RON	SOILC	ReNDiS	BATHW	OSTREOPSIS	PEST	PLACE
Findability		100							
	keyword usage	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
	categories	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
	geo search	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	time based search	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Accessibility		100							
	access url	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	download url	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	download url accessibility	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Interoperability		110							
	format	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	media type	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	standard format mediatype	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	non proprietary format	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	machine readable format	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	DCAT-AP compliance	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Reusability		75							
	licence information	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	licence_vocabulary	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	access restriction	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

	access restriction vocabulary	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	contact point	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	publisher	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Contextuality		15							
	rights	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	file size	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	date of issue	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	modification date	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Global rating		400							

4.2 Linked Open Datasets – ARIA

The innovation and procurement regional Company of Lombardy Region³⁰ (ARIA) produced and published 10 RDF distributions of as many datasets. The details for each distribution are reported in the following subsections. All the resources in the RDF distribution use persistent URIs by means of the w3id.org³¹ service run by the Permanent Identifier Community Group³². The base namespace adopted by ARIA is:

`https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/`

and URIs are generated following the schema

`https://w3id.org/italia/lombardia/data/{entity_type}/{entity_id}`

where:

- `entity_type` is the placeholder the the entity type, e.g. `observationseries`;
- `entity_it` is the placeholder for the entity identifier, e.g. `00105_an15_airpressure_202201`.

Accordingly, <https://w3id.org/italia/lombardia/data/health-agency/030325> is an example of URI generated to uniquely and persistently identify the Health Protection Agencies (ATS) of Bergamo.

Table 13 reports the properties of the Italian Profile of DCAT-AP³³ (DCAPT-AP_IT) used for metadating all the data produced by ARIA at dataset and distribution level, respectively.

³⁰ The Italian name is: Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale

³¹ <https://w3id.org/>

³² <https://www.w3.org/community/perma-id/>

³³ <https://www.dati.gov.it/content/dcat-ap-it-v10-profilo-italiano-dcat-ap-0>

Table 13. DCAT properties used by ISPRA.

Subject	DCAT property
Dataset	<p>Mandatory properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dct:identifier * ● dct:title * ● dct:description * ● dcat:theme * ● dct:modified * ● dct:rightsHolder * ● dct:accrualPeriodicity * <p>Recommended properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:contactPoint * ● dct:publisher * <p>Optional properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:keyword ● dct:temporal * ● dct:spatial * ● dct:accessRights
Distribution	<p>Mandatory properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:accessURL ● dct:format * ● dct:license * <p>Recommended properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dct:description ● dct:title <p>Optional properties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● dcat:downloadURL ● dct:rights ● dct:issued

4.2.1 Hydrography Rivers

The Hydrography Rivers RDF dataset is linked to Wikidata and DBpedia and was been obtained by applying the RML rules³⁴ to datasets on the monitoring of the quality of rivers³⁵. This dataset serves the WHOW Use

³⁴ <https://rml.io/>

³⁵

https://github.com/whow-project/datasets/blob/main/RML-RULES/hydrography/rivers/RMLRulesRiversLinking_pyml.ttl

Case 2³⁶ [3]. In fact, the dataset contains the results of periodic checks carried out on water intended for human consumption by the Health Protection Agencies (ATS) through the structures of the SIAN (Food Hygiene and Nutrition Service). The SIAN is responsible for the control and monitoring of the hygienic and sanitary quality of food and beverages, including drinking and mineral water, at all stages. The frequency of water quality monitoring and the parameters to be monitored are established by Legislative Decree 31/2001³⁷.

Table 14 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Hydrography Rivers.

Table 14. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hydrography Rivers.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:description	Il dataset contiene i risultati dei controlli periodici effettuati sulle acque destinate al consumo umano da parte delle ATS attraverso le strutture del SIAN (Servizio Igiene degli alimenti e Nutrizione). Al SIAN compete il controllo e la sorveglianza della qualità igienico-sanitaria degli alimenti e bevande, comprese le acque potabili e minerali, in tutte le fasi. La frequenza di monitoraggio della qualità dell'acqua di prelievo e i parametri da monitorare sono stabiliti dal Decreto Legislativo 31/2001.@it
	dct:identifier	:beda-kb7b
	dct:modified	2019-12-31^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	Qualità delle acque destinate al consumo umano - dettaglio parametri@it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>
	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://www.arpalombardia.it>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/beda-kb7b>;
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/beda-kb7b>
	dcat:keyword	'qualità delle acque'@it
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:description	Distribuzione RDF del dataset contiene i risultati dei controlli periodici effettuati sulle acque destinate al consumo umano da parte delle ATS attraverso le strutture del SIAN (Servizio Igiene degli alimenti e Nutrizione). Al SIAN compete il

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685761>

³⁷

<https://www.portaleacque.salute.gov.it/PortaleAcquePubblico/normativa.do?lang=en#:~:text=The%20%22quality%20of%20water%20intended,origin%20and%20type%20of%20delivery.>

		controllo e la sorveglianza della qualità igienico-sanitaria degli alimenti e bevande, comprese le acque potabili e minerali, in tutte le fasi. La frequenza di monitoraggio della qualità dell'acqua di prelievo e i parametri da monitorare sono stabiliti dal Decreto Legislativo 31/2001.@it
	dct:title	Distribuzione RDF della dataset sulla qualità delle acque destinate al consumo umano - dettaglio parametri@it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/beda-kb7b/rows.ttl?accessType
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.2 Hydrography Lakes

The Hydrography Lakes RDF dataset is linked to Wikidata and DBpedia and was been obtained by applying the RML rules³⁸ to datasets on the monitoring of the quality of lakes³⁹. This dataset serves the WHOW Use Case 2 [3]. In fact, the dataset collects analytical data on the substances monitored at points in the Lombardy Region lake monitoring network.

Table 15 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Hydrography Lakes.

Table 15. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hydrography Lakes.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://www.arpalombardia.it>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/d4ep-yvbw>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/d4ep-yvbw>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:description	Il dataset raccoglie i dati analitici relativi alle sostanze monitorate sui punti della rete di monitoraggio dei laghi della Regione Lombardia.@it

³⁸ <https://rml.io/>

³⁹

https://github.com/whow-project/datasets/blob/main/RML-RULES/hydrography/lakes/RMLMappinghydrolakes_pyrml.ttl

	dct:identifier	:d4ep-yvbw
	dct:modified	2023-06-05^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	Dati analitici corpi idrici lacustri@it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>
	dcat:keyword	'qualit delle acque'@it, 'water quality'@en, dcat:keyword,'corpi idrici lacustri'@it dcat:keyword,'lake water bodies'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:description	Distribuzione RDF del dataset che raccoglie i dati analitici relativi alle sostanze monitorate sui punti della rete di monitoraggio dei laghi della Regione Lombardia.@it
	dct:title	Distribuzione RDF dei dati analitici corpi idrici lacustri@it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/d4ep-yvbw/rows.ttl?accessType
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.3 Water quality parameters

The dataset contains the results of periodic checks carried out on water intended for human consumption by the ATS through the structures of the SIAN (Food Hygiene and Nutrition Service). The SIAN is responsible for the control and monitoring of the hygienic and sanitary quality of food and beverages, including drinking and mineral water, at all stages. The frequency of water quality monitoring and the parameters to be monitored are established by Legislative Decree 31/2001.

Table 16 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Water quality parameters.

Table 16. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Water quality parameters.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/beda-kb7b>
	dct:rightsHolder	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>,

		<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAD>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/beda-kb7b>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:description	Il dataset contiene i risultati dei controlli periodici effettuati sulle acque destinate al consumo umano da parte delle ATS attraverso le strutture del SIAN (Servizio Igiene degli alimenti e Nutrizione). Al SIAN compete il controllo e la sorveglianza della qualità igienico-sanitaria degli alimenti e bevande, comprese le acque potabili e minerali, in tutte le fasi. La frequenza di monitoraggio della qualità dell'acqua di prelievo e i parametri da monitorare sono stabiliti dal Decreto Legislativo 31/2001.@it
	dct:identifier	':beda-kb7b'
	dct:modified	2019-12-31^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	'Qualità delle acque destinate al consumo umano - dettaglio parametri'@it
	dcat:keyword	'qualità delle acque'@it, 'water quality'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF del dataset che raccoglie i dati analitici sulla qualità delle acque in Lombardia.'@it
	dct:description	"La distribuzione RDF contiene i risultati dei controlli periodici effettuati sulle acque destinate al consumo umano da parte delle ATS attraverso le strutture del SIAN (Servizio Igiene degli alimenti e Nutrizione). Al SIAN compete il controllo e la sorveglianza della qualità igienico-sanitaria degli alimenti e bevande, comprese le acque potabili e minerali, in tutte le fasi. La frequenza di monitoraggio della qualità dell'acqua di prelievo e i parametri da monitorare sono stabiliti dal Decreto Legislativo 31/2001."@it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/beda-kb7b/rows.ttl?accessType
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.4 Underground waters

The dataset collects analytical data on substances monitored at points in the groundwater monitoring network of the Lombardy Region.

Table 17 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Underground waters.

Table 17. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Underground waters.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:description	'Il dataset raccoglie i dati analitici relativi alle sostanze monitorate sui punti della rete di monitoraggio delle acque sotterranee della Regione Lombardia.'@it
	dct:identifier	':46wy-4ydd'
	dct:modified	'2023-05-02'^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	Dati analitici acque sotterranee@it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>, <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://www.arpalombardia.it>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/46wy-4ydd>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/46wy-4ydd>
	dcat:keyword	'acque sotterranee'@it, 'underground water'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF del dataset delle acque sotterranee in Lombardia.'@it
	dct:description	La distribuzione RDF contiene i dati analitici relativi alle sostanze monitorate sui punti della rete di monitoraggio delle acque sotterranee della Regione Lombardia.@it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/46wy-4ydd/rows.ttl?accessType>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.5 Height of lakes

The RDF dataset contains data on lake heights in the Region of Lombardy. Table 18 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Height of lakes.

Table 18. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Height of lakes.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/ANNUAL>
	dct:description	Dataset con l'altezza dei laghi della Regione Lombardia@it
	dct:identifier	:xiye-qjzy
	dct:modified	2023-04-03^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	'Altezza laghi'@it, 'Height of lakes'@en
	dcat:theme	'
	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:rightsHolder	<https://www.arpalombardia.it>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/xiye-qjzy>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/xiye-qjzy>
	dcat:keyword	'altezza laghi'@it, 'height of lakes'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:title	'Distribuzione RDF del dataset delle altezze dei laghi in Lombardia.'@it
	dct:description	La distribuzione RDF contiene i dati sulle altezze dei laghi della Regione Lombardia.@it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/xiye-qjzy/rows.ttl?accessType>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.6 ATS

This dataset contains data about the Health Protection Agencies (ATS) located in Lombardy region. The Health Protection Agencies have as one of their tasks the annual planning of health promotion

interventions, integrating the various professional and organisational skills within the Agencies as well as the roles and responsibilities - activated through participatory processes - of the various community actors (Municipalities, Institutions, Bodies, Voluntary work, Associations, etc.). that contribute to health results in the population. Table 19 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for ATS.

Table 19. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for ATS.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/UNKNOWN>
	dct:description	Dataset con gli ATS della Regione Lombardia@it
	dct:identifier	:h55m-dqi2
	dct:modified	2023-07-28^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:rightsHolder	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	ATS@it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>
	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/h55m-dqi2>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/h55m-dqi2>
	dcat:keyword	'ats'@it, 'Agenzie di Tutela della Salute'@it, 'hpa'@en, 'Health Protection Agencies'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:description	'Distribuzione RDF del dataset con gli ATS della Regione Lombardia'@it
	dct:title	ATS - RDF distribution
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF> ;
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10> ;
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/h55m-dqi2/rows.rdf?accessType>
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.7 Hospital stays

This dataset is a valuable resource providing in-depth insights into the critical aspects of hospital management and patient care. This dataset focuses on the averages of hospital stays and accesses, offering

a comprehensive view of the healthcare landscape in Lombardy region. In today's dynamic healthcare environment, understanding the duration of hospital stays and the frequency of hospital accesses is crucial for policymakers, healthcare professionals, and researchers alike. This dataset aims to facilitate evidence-based decision-making by shedding light on key metrics that influence the efficiency and effectiveness of healthcare delivery.

Table 20 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Hospital stays.

Table 20. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hospital stays.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/UNKNOWN>
	dct:description	Dataset Degenza Media E Accessi Medi Per ACC E Struttura@it
	dct:identifier	r_lombar:rzni-6n8h
	dct:modified	2018-02-23^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:rightsHolder	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:spatial	<https://www.geonames.org/3174618>
	dct:title	Dataset Degenza Media E Accessi Medi Per ACC E Struttura@it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/rzni-6n8h>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/rzni-6n8h>
	dct:keyword	'accessi medi'@it, 'average accesses'@en, 'degenze ospedaliere'@it, 'hospital stays'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:description	Distribuzione RDF su degenza media e accessi medi per ACC e struttura@it
	dct:title	Degenze ospedaliere - RDF
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/rzni-6n8h/rows.ttl?accessType
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.8 Drugs

This dataset provides an in-depth exploration of drug consumption, presenting averages, trends, and distribution patterns across various demographic groups and medical specialties. By delving into the nuances of drug utilisation in Lombardy, users can gain valuable insights into the evolving needs of the population, potential areas for intervention, and opportunities for healthcare optimization.

Table 21 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Drugs.

Table 21. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hospital Drugs.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/UNKNOWN>
	dct:description	Dataset sul consumo di farmaci in Regione Lombardia per ATC di I livello@it
	dct:identifier	:2mr3-henm
	dct:modified	2019-01-08^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:rightsHolder	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	Consumo Di Farmaci In Regione Lombardia Per ATC I livello@it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>
	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/2mr3-henm>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/2mr3-henm>
	dct:keyword	'consumo farmaci'@it, 'drug consumption'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:description	Distribuzione RDF sul consumo di farmaci in Regione Lombardia per ATC di I livello@it
	dct:title	Consumo Di Farmaci In Regione Lombardia Per ATC I livello in RDF@it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/2mr3-henm/rows.ttl?accessType
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.9 Infectious diseases

This dataset contains numbers of registered cases and rates by age and gender, of infectious diseases detected in the Lombardy Region.

Table 22 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Infectious diseases.

Table 22. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Hospital Infectious diseases.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/UNKNOWN>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/fvk5-jiuq>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/fvk5-jiuq>
	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:description	Numero pratiche registrate e tassi per et [†] e genere, delle malattie infettive rilevate in Regione Lombardia@it
	dct:identifier	:fvk5-jiuq
	dct:modified	2023-11-15^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:rightsHolder	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	Malattie infettive Tassi Regione Lombardia per sesso e et [†] @it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>
	dct:keyword	'malattie infettive'@it, dct:keyword,'infectious diseases'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:description	Distribuzione RDF del dataset con il numero pratiche registrate e tassi per et [†] e genere, delle malattie infettive rilevate in Regione Lombardia@it
	dct:title	Distribuzione RDF delle malattie infettive Tassi Regione Lombardia per sesso e et [†] @it
	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/fvk5-jiuq/rows.ttl?accessType
	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>

4.2.10 Weather

A concise yet powerful compilation of weather data providing a snapshot of climatic conditions in the Lombardy Region. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for meteorologists, researchers, and enthusiasts seeking to understand the weather patterns that characterise this diverse and dynamic region.

Table 23 reports the values associated with the properties of DCAPT-AP_IT for Weather.

Table 23. DCAPT-AP_IT properties for Weather.

Subject	DCAT-AP_IT property	Value
Dataset	dct:accrualPeriodicity	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/UNKNOWN>
	dct:temporal	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/period-time/fvk5-jiuq>
	dcat:contactpoint	<https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/d/contact-point/fvk5-jiuq>
	dct:spatial	<https://sws.geonames.org/3174618/>
	dct:description	Numero pratiche registrate e tassi per et [†] e genere, delle malattie infettive rilevate in Regione Lombardia@it
	dct:identifier	:fvk5-jiuq
	dct:modified	2023-11-15^^xsd:date
	dct:publisher	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:rightsHolder	<http://www.regione.lombardia.it>
	dct:title	Malattie infettive Tassi Regione Lombardia per sesso e et [†] @it
	dcat:theme	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/HEAL>
	dct:keyword	'malattie infettive'@it, dct:keyword,'infectious diseases'@en
	dct:accessRights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
Distribution	dct:format	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_TURTLE>
	dct:license	<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A11_CCO10>
	dct:description	Distibuzione RDF dei dati meteorologici che fornisce un'istantanea delle condizioni climatiche della Regione Lombardia. Questo set di dati [√] ® una risorsa preziosa per meteorologi, ricercatori e appassionati che cercano di comprendere i modelli meteorologici che caratterizzano questa regione diversificata e dinamica.@it
	dct:title	Distribuzione RDF dei dati meteo Regione Lombardia@it
	dcat:accessURL	<https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>
	dcat:downloadURL	<https://www.dati.lombardia.it/api/views/647i-nhvk/rows.ttl?accessType,DOWNLOAD>

	dct:rights	<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
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4.2.11 Metadata Quality Assessment

Table 24 reports the results we recorded according to the MQA Methodology formalised by the official portal for European data computed with the metadata validation tool of the WHOW Toolkit described in [Chapter 3](#). The global rating recorded is 390 for all the datasets provided by ISPRA and their corresponding RDF distributions. This result is rated as excellent according to the range of points established by the MQA formalised by the official portal for European data.

Table 24. Results obtained for the metadata of ISPRA datasets and RDF distributions.

Dim,	Indicator	Hydro Rivers	Hydro Lakes	Water q. params	Und. water	Height of lakes	ATS	Hosp. stays	Drugs	Inf. diseases	Weather
Findability		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	keyword usage	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
	categories	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
	geo search	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	time based search	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Access.		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	access url	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	download url	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	download url accessibility	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Interoper.		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	format	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	media type	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	standard format mediatype	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	non proprietary format	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	machine readable format	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	DCAT-AP	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

	compliance										
Reusab.		75									
	licence information	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	licence_vocabulary	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	access restriction	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	access restriction vocabulary	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	contact point	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
	publisher	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Context.		15									
	rights	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	file size	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	date of issue	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	modification date	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Global rating		390									

5 Conclusions

Merely releasing open data falls short of meeting requirements. It should not only address relevant public inquiries but also uphold a consistently high standard. In response to the Open Knowledge Foundation's recommended shift in focus, this deliverable introduces a comprehensive data quality assessment framework. In this deliverable we presented the WHOW metadata quality framework and its compliance with the Metadata Quality Assessment tool of the European portal for open data. The framework incorporates the Metadata Quality Assessment Methodology of the European data portal. Consequently, we employ this framework to evaluate the compliance of metadata associated with all RDF datasets generated by the project's two data providers (ISPRA and ARIA), constituting the WHOW Knowledge Graph, with the DCAT-AP standards. Each RDF dataset is thoroughly examined, presenting utilised metadata and documenting the corresponding quality score in a detailed report.

References

- [1] Publications Office of the European Union., *Open data maturity report 2021*. LU: Publications Office, 2022. Accessed: Nov. 30, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2830/394148>
- [2] Research Data Alliance FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, 'FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines', 2020, doi: 10.15497/RDA00050.
- [3] M. Picone, G. Carletti, C. Ciciriello, and P. Esposito, 'Use Cases Definition', Dec. 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6685761.
- [4] J. Nogueras-Iso, J. Lacasta, M. A. Urena-Camara, and F. J. Ariza-Lopez, 'Quality of Metadata in Open Data Portals', *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 60364–60382, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3073455.
- [5] B. Šlibar, D. Oreški, and N. Begičević Ređep, 'Importance of the Open Data Assessment: An Insight Into the (Meta) Data Quality Dimensions', *SAGE Open*, vol. 11, no. 2, p. 215824402110231, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1177/21582440211023178.
- [6] A. S. Lippolis *et al.*, 'Milestone #9: SDGs and KPIs are defined', Apr. 2022, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6685733.
- [7] S. C. Mana and T. Sasiprabha, 'A Study on Various Semantic Metadata Standards to Improve Data Usability', in *2019 International Conference on Computational Intelligence in Data Science (ICCIDS)*, Chennai, India: IEEE, Feb. 2019, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1109/ICCIDS.2019.8862044.
- [8] A. Bobasheva, F. Gandon, and F. Precioso, 'Learning and Reasoning for Cultural Metadata Quality: Coupling Symbolic AI and Machine Learning over a Semantic Web Knowledge Graph to Support Museum Curators in Improving the Quality of Cultural Metadata and Information Retrieval', *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1–23, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1145/3485844.
- [9] K. Bugbee *et al.*, 'Improving Discovery and Use of NASA's Earth Observation Data Through Metadata Quality Assessments', *Data Sci. J.*, vol. 20, p. 17, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.5334/dsj-2021-017.
- [10] Y.-N. Chen, C.-Y. Wen, H.-P. Chen, Y.-H. Lin, and H.-C. Sum, 'Metrics for Metadata Quality Assurance and Their Implications for Digital Libraries', in *Digital Libraries: For Cultural Heritage, Knowledge Dissemination, and Future Creation*, vol. 7008, C. Xing, F. Crestani, and A. Rauber, Eds., in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 7008. , Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 138–147. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-24826-9_19.
- [11] K. J. Reiche and E. Höfig, 'Implementation of Metadata Quality Metrics and Application on Public Government Data', in *2013 IEEE 37th Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference Workshops*, 2013, pp. 236–241. doi: 10.1109/COMPASACW.2013.32.
- [12] V. Segarra-Faggioni and A. Romero-Pelaez, 'Automatic classification of OER for metadata quality assessment', in *2022 International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT)*, Bucharest, Romania: IEEE, Jul. 2022, pp. 16–18. doi: 10.1109/ICALT55010.2022.00011.
- [13] D. Gavrilis *et al.*, 'Measuring Quality in Metadata Repositories', in *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries*, vol. 9316, S. Kapidakis, C. Mazurek, and M. Werla, Eds., in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 9316. , Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 56–67. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-24592-8_5.
- [14] D. M. Nichols, C.-H. Chan, D. Bainbridge, D. McKay, and M. B. Twidale, 'A lightweight metadata quality tool', in *Proceedings of the 8th ACM/IEEE-CS joint conference on Digital libraries*, Pittsburgh PA PA USA: ACM, Jun. 2008, pp. 385–388. doi: 10.1145/1378889.1378957.
- [15] D. Mouromtsev, P. Haase, E. Cherny, D. Pavlov, A. Andreev, and A. Spiridonova, 'Towards the Russian Linked Culture Cloud: Data Enrichment and Publishing', in *The Semantic Web. Latest Advances and New Domains*, vol. 9088, F. Gandon, M. Sabou, H. Sack, C. d'Amato, P. Cudré-Mauroux, and A. Zimmermann, Eds., in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 9088. , Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 637–651. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-18818-8_39.
- [16] S. Neumaier, J. Umbrich, and A. Polleres, 'Automated Quality Assessment of Metadata across Open Data

-
- Portals', *J. Data Inf. Qual.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–29, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1145/2964909.
- [17] A. Vetrò, L. Canova, M. Torchiano, C. O. Minotas, R. Iemma, and F. Morando, 'Open data quality measurement framework: Definition and application to Open Government Data', *Gov. Inf. Q.*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 325–337, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.giq.2016.02.001.
- [18] R. Máchová and M. Lnenicka, 'Evaluating the Quality of Open Data Portals on the National Level', *J. Theor. Appl. Electron. Commer. Res.*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 21–41, 2017, doi: 10.4067/S0718-18762017000100003.
- [19] X. Zhu and M. A. Freeman, 'An evaluation of U.S. municipal open data portals: A user interaction framework', *J. Assoc. Inf. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 27–37, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1002/asi.24081.
- [20] A. S. Lippolis, G. Lodi, and A. G. Nuzzolese, 'Design of the technical services for knowledge graph management', Nov. 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6685697.